

FORRT Replication Hub

April, 2026

Conditions under which R2 will be discontinued after a runtime of 26 months

OSF project: <https://osf.io/kupqt/>

We, the editorial board of Replication Research (R2), will dissolve the journal on January 31st, 2028 unless **all** of the following conditions are met:

#	Condition	Explanation
1	At least 12 research articles have been submitted. Up to 17% of these may include members of the editorial board. The inaugural editorial does not count towards the 12 submissions.	Researchers are using the service that we provide.
2	At least 10 research articles have been published as “online first” articles or in the final layout. The inaugural editorial does not count towards the 10 published articles.	Editing and reviewing manuscripts works efficiently. 10 publications in 2 years allows for inclusion in the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ).
3	At least 5 research articles have been published as “online first” articles or in the final layout in 2027.	There is continuous support of the journal (in contrast to an initial wave of submissions followed by no submissions).

4	The editorial team consists of at least six people.	There are several people contributing to the journal and making sure that the service works efficiently.
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Comments

- The conditions will be checked on Monday, January 10 2028 at noon CET by the editor-in-chief.
- A brief report about the criteria and observed numbers will be published on Zenodo and sent to all members of the editorial team by January 17. An announcement on the journal website with a link to the report and a decision will be posted.
- The editorial team will meet in January or February 2028 to discuss follow-up conditions for the next term.
- Members of the editorial team are described in the journal's constitution.
- If the editors are from two or fewer different disciplines, the editorial team will discuss a name change for the journal. Disciplines are determined by the field in which the editorial team member completed their PhD.
- Articles that are submitted before the publication of the decision on January 17th will continue to go through the entire editorial process from submission to publication. A discontinuation means that no new submissions will be accepted.
- The editorial team can at any point make the decision to discontinue the journal but it cannot overwrite the decision to continue the journal.

Amendment (Version 2 from 23 April, 2026)

Since the initial preregistration of these conditions, Replication Research (R2) has actively sought structural funding to support a comprehensive removal of barriers to replications. If major structural funding (that is, a three-year DFG LIS grant) is secured, the original discontinuation date of January 31, 2028, will be formally suspended, as the grant specifically provides the resources (e.g., dedicated staff, workshops, policy interventions) designed to scale the journal. In the event of successful funding, these four conditions will no longer serve as a 'stopping rule', but rather as rigid Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for an interim evaluation at Month 26 of the project. Should the KPIs not be met at that point, the editorial board and the grant personnel will discuss pivoting target disciplines and merging workflows with RJF partners instead of immediate dissolution

The R2 Senior Editors

23 April 2026

Lukas Röseler, Lukas Wallrich, Flavio Azevedo